

Plectranthus zuluensis

Zulu spurflower

© P. Candotti

Group: Eudicot

Size: 2 meters

Distribution:

Plectranthus zuluensis occurs from the northern parts of the Eastern Cape through the coastal region of KwaZulu-Natal to southern Swaziland. It grows along stream banks and in river gorges in shady or semi-shady areas on the margins of semi-coastal, subtropical forests.

Importance:

The Zulu spurflower is cultivated locally and internationally as a flowering ornamental plant, valued for its velvety foliage and blue to mauve blooms.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 11.03 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.64 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.48 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.1% [Single: 73.6%, Duplicated: 23.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 172.11 kilobases

Contig number: 4 569

Sample Contributor contact details:

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